

D4.4

Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules for IWW and connected hinterland infrastructures final version

Project name

Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes

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List of definitions, abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
C	Capacity
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
COP	Common Operational Picture
D	Demand
DDF	Depth-Damage Function
DM	Damage Measure
DS	Damage State
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EDP	Engineering Demand Parameter
IM	Intensity Measure
IMS	Incident Management System
IWAT	IWW Assessment Tool
IWW	Inland WaterWays
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LS	Limit State
MHVM	Multi-Hazard-Vulnerability-Modules
MSA	Multi-stripe Analysis
Mx	Month x
PBEE	Performance-Based Earthquake Engineering
PGA	Peak Ground Acceleration
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
S _a	Spectral acceleration
Tx.x	Task x.x
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The PLOTO project aims to increase the resilience of the Inland WaterWays (IWW) infrastructures and the connected hinterland infrastructures, thus ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents, and other kind of hazards. PLOTO's main target is to combine downscaled climate change scenarios (applied to IWW infrastructures) with simulation tools and actual data, to provide the relevant authorities and their operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at strategic and operational levels. The PLOTO integrated platform and its tools will be validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary.

The aim of this report is to:

- a. present the finalized methodology behind the development of the Multi-Hazard-Vulnerability-Modules (MHVM) as described in Task 4.2 of WP4;
- b. index the IWW and hinterland infrastructure elements (assets) that constitute the exposure model of PLOTO;
- c. present the structure of MHVMs.

1. Introduction

1.1 Project information

The project entitled **“Deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes (PLOTTO)”** aims at increasing the resilience of the IWW and the connected hinterland infrastructures, especially under adverse conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents and other kinds of hazards. In doing this, downscaled climate change scenarios will be combined with simulation tools and actual data, to provide operators an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at strategic and operational levels.

PLOTTO project consists in the deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies, and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extremes. An integrated tool is set up to allow relevant authorities to improve the efficiency of their infrastructure management. This tool is a combination of downscaled climate change scenarios with simulation tools and actual data. Six complementary avenues will be considered to achieve this integrated tool that will support relevant authorities and their operators for more effective management:

- Measure and use high-resolution modelling data for the determination and assessment of the climatic risk of the selected transport infrastructures and associated expected damages.
- Use existing data from various sources with new types of sensor-generated data (computer vision) to feed the used simulator.
- Utilise tailored weather forecasts (combining seamlessly all available data sources) for specific hot spots, providing real-time early warnings with corresponding impact assessment.
- Develop improved multi-temporal, multi-sensor UAV- and satellite-based observations with robust spectral analysis, computer vision, and machine learning-based assessment for diverse transport infrastructures.
- Design and implement an integrated resilience assessment platform environment as an innovative planning tool that will permit a quantitative resilience assessment through an end-to-end simulation environment, running “what-if” impact/risk/resilience assessment scenarios. The effects of adaptation measures can be investigated by changing the hazard, exposure, and vulnerability input parameters.
- Design and implement a Common Operational Picture (COP), including an enhanced visualisation interface and an Incident Management System (IMS).

The PLOTTO integrated platform and its tools will be validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

Deliverable D4.4 “Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules for IWW and connected hinterland infrastructures final version” is one of the two (2) deliverables of WP4 related to Task 4.2 “Development of vulnerability modules”.

The following description outlines the individual tasks conducted within the Task 4.2:

- Formation of the exposure model of Inland Waterways (IWW) and hinterland infrastructure assets per PLOTTO demonstration case (A: Romania, B: Hungary, and C: Belgium).
- Separate asset-wise analysis of each hazard based on the location of the asset and the natural hazards associated with the site of interest.
- Categorizing the assets into critical and less important yet non-negligible ones, applying detailed, asset-specific vulnerability analysis for the critical assets, and using reduced-order class-specific models for the less critical assets.
- Large-scale vulnerability assessment of the assets after simulating their response against natural hazard stressors. Generation of multiple intensity-to-consequences scenarios per asset or per class of assets given potential hazards that threaten the asset.
- Design of a flood vulnerability assessment tool to quantify the direct economic loss for each asset within a floodplain via computation of flood damage factors and usage of an asset valuation model.
- Development of Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules: Encoding of simulation results into software libraries, termed Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules, which enable a seamless integration of hazard simulators and vulnerability results into the IWAT model of the IWW system.

To summarize, D4.4 aims to:

- a. present the finalized methodology behind the development of the Multi-Hazard-Vulnerability-Modules (MHVM) as described in Task 4.2 of Work Package WP4;
- b. index the characteristic IWW and interconnected non-IWW elements (assets) that constitute the exposure model of PLOTTO;
- c. present the typical structure of MHVMs.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

This deliverable is related to PLOTTO Objectives STO-5 and STO-8. The MHVMs are standardisable software libraries that feed the Risk Assessment Engine. They provide data in a human-readable format regarding the fragility and vulnerability of IWAT assets against natural hazards. The objective is to acquire vulnerability assessment for assets related to IWW. This involves evaluating the impact of multiple hazards, including climate-related loads (such as rain, wind, etc.), geo-hazard intensities (e.g. ground acceleration), and man-made hazards (e.g. traffic and impact loads).

1.3 Intended audience

Deliverable 4.4 is public and thus, it will be openly available to all stakeholders. Those include public authorities, IWW and other hinterland infrastructure owners and operators, researchers, technology providers, as well as decision and policy makers.

The deliverable focuses on presenting Inland WaterWays end-user needs and requirements related to the design and development of a system that improves the resilience of IWW against climate change and other extreme events.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

The Deliverable has been structured as follows:

- Section 1. Describes PLOTTO's aim, as well as this document's purpose, intended audience, and structure.
- Section 2. Describes the methodology followed in this deliverable.
- Section 3. Describes the theoretical background that is adopted for the development of MHVMs.
- Section 4. Describes the assets comprising the exposure model per Demonstration Case.
- Section 5. Describes the typical structure of MHVMs.
- Section 6. Concludes the deliverable by summarising the main outcomes.

2. Methodology

This deliverable is linked to Task 4.2 “Development of vulnerability modules (M6-M24; NTUA)”. In more detail, it includes: (a) indexing of the IWW and non-IWW assets that are selected for the development of the exposure model of PLOT0 demonstration cases, (b) presenting the methodology employed for assessing the vulnerability of assets under natural or man-made hazards, and (c) presenting the development of MHVMs libraries (T4.2).

Figure 1 presents the WP4 high-level architecture where the Physical Vulnerability Assessment module (related to T4.2) is depicted. Also, Figure 1 illustrates the interconnection of T4.2 with the rest of the modules of WP4. Essentially, MHVMs are generated offline using structural and geotechnical safety assessment simulators. To elaborate, hazard simulators analyze inputs for selected hazard scenarios and transfer their outcomes to IWAT. Then, IWAT forwards the hazard input to MHVMs to conduct risk and resilience assessments. The outcomes are then sent back to the middleware for storage.

Figure 1: WP4 high-level architecture (adopted from D2.2)

To meet the objectives of the Deliverable, the contributing partners of T4.2 have cooperated closely, and communicated via WP4 coordination meetings and dedicated bilateral meetings with the end-users. The time plan and milestones of the ongoing work on T4.2 is schematically illustrated in Figure 2. Technical partners worked towards achieving STO-5 “Improved vulnerability analysis and resilience assessment, including digital winning tools to simulate IWW.”, STO-8 “To establish long-term data platforms securing open, consistent data points...”, and the relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The methodology that was implemented followed three steps as below:

- 1) Definition of the assets (IWW and non-IWW elements) which constitute the exposure model of PLOTO demonstration cases based on experts’ opinions and the relevant data provided by the (local) technical partners – stakeholders per demonstration case.
- 2) Finalized PLOTO’s exposure model.
- 3) Design of MHVMs based on state-of-the-art tools that can be employed for assessing resilience of structures/infrastructures against natural and/or man-made hazards.

The work in T4.2 is progressing with the finalization of the exposure model of PLOTO and the corresponding finalization of MHVMs libraries (based on the work made on T4.1). All the work employed for the development of D4.3 and D4.4 was realized in coordination with the technical partners of the relative WPs and Tasks.

Figure 2: Time plan and milestones of T4.2

3. Theoretical background

3.1 Definitions

Hazard: stressors associated with a threat whose occurrence may affect the normal activities of people and the integrity and functionality of IWW and non-IWW assets, including, for example, ground shaking for earthquakes or wind action for storms.

Intensity Measure: Interface variable that links the hazard analysis and the structural analysis.

Engineering Demand Parameter: Quantity of structural response that is used to measure the response and to estimate damage to structural and non-structural components and systems.

Fragility curve: Function that provides for a structure the probability of exceeding a given limit state, or equivalently of being in a damage state or worse, given the intensity measure.

Vulnerability curve: Function that provides the distribution of a loss measure given the level of the intensity measure.

Exposure model: Contains information on the assets at risk, their location, taxonomy, etc.

3.2 IM approach

The analytical estimation of losses involves the combination of hazard (climate-related, geo-hazard, and man-made hazard) with the results of (geo)structural analyses. The former is performed by experts per field (e.g., seismologists, environmental engineers, etc.), whereas the latter is performed by engineers. Typically, an intensity measure (IM) is employed as the interface variable between the hazard analysis and (geo)structural analysis. IM serves as a point of contact between the different disciplines aiming to incorporate all complexity of the hazard-specific loading into a single quantity that can be used for the (geo)structural analysis. The aim is to avoid considering all the diverse characteristics of the loading. For instance, considering earthquakes, seismologists estimate the statistical properties of the IM through Probabilistic Seismic Hazard Analysis (Cornell 1968), while engineers calculate the structural response for given levels of the IM without taking into account a complex combination of earthquake magnitude, source-to-structure distance, and other relevant seismological parameters within structural analysis. The desirable dissociation is achieved by selecting an appropriate IM that is efficient and sufficient with respect to the characteristics of the type of hazard examined (e.g. Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2005; Luco and Cornell 2007; Kazantzi and Vamvatsikos 2015; Lachanas et al. 2023). Efficiency of an IM means that the selected IM should be a good predictor of the (geo)structural response, as measured by the structure's selected Engineering Demand Parameter (EDP). This enables achieving the desirable level of accuracy on the numerical analysis results with a relatively small number of time-history analyses. IM sufficiency means that the selected IM should show low dependency on the other inherent characteristics of the hazard rendering an asset's response independent of these specific characteristics. For instance, regarding the seismic risk assessment, a sufficient IM would remove any bias from considering the magnitude, distance, and other seismological parameters of the ground motion records rather than the IM. Efficiency and sufficiency goals do not inherently align, as efficiency targets a decrease in variability within dynamic

analysis results, while sufficiency focuses on diminishing reliance on hazard characteristics rather than the IM. It's crucial to recognize that by using a more efficient IM, despite reducing the dispersion in response, it doesn't necessarily mean an overall reduction in risk variability. Instead, it might involve shifting part of the variability to a different level within the risk estimation assessment.

In the PLOTO framework, for each type of hazard an appropriate IM is selected, as presented in Table 1. In the case of geo-hazard (earthquake), PGA is the peak ground acceleration and $S_a(T)$ is the elastic spectral acceleration for a vibration period T .

Table 1: Natural hazards considered in PLOTO and pertinent intensity measure (IM)

Hazard	IM
Weather	Wind speed/direction/gust factor, temperature, precipitation, etc.
Flood hazard	water level
Seismic hazard	$PGA, S_a(T)$

3.3 IM – EDP relationship approach

In the context of structural analysis, each dynamic analysis produces a simple pair of IM and the corresponding EDP demand values. Given the inherent uncertainties, multiple analyses involving a considerable number of inputs per intensity level are required. For example, in the case of seismic hazard, multiple ground motion records are employed as inputs for the analysis at each discrete IM level. There are many ways to group the aforementioned IM-EDP pairs in order to adequately characterize the IM-EDP space and estimate the seismic demand, such as single-stripe analysis (Jalayer 2003), multi-stripe analysis (Jalayer 2003; Jalayer and Cornell 2009), cloud analysis (Jalayer 2003; Mackie and Stojadinović 2001; Padgett and DesRoches 2008), or incremental dynamic analysis (Vamvatsikos and Cornell 2002). In the PLOTO framework, the multi-stripe analysis (MSA) method is employed for grouping IM-EDP pairs as it facilitates the post-processing procedure without the need for fitting regression models. MSA consists of a group of stripe analyses, each of which is performed at a different IM level. A single stripe includes the EDP results of the structure at hand when subjected to n time-histories of the hazard with each of them being scaled at the certain IM level of the stripe. A characteristic example of single-stripe analysis is shown in Figure 3, where, for a structure, each point (star) indicates the result of the non-linear time-history dynamic analysis under a ground motion record scaled to $S_a(T)=0.94g$. For this example, the first-mode spectral acceleration $S_a(T)$ is employed as IM, where T is set equal to the fundamental vibration period of the structure. By performing non-linear dynamic analyses for multiple intensity levels (multiple stripes), the MSA results are obtained, as indicatively illustrated in Figure 4. Moreover, state-of-the-art tools are used to select time-histories in order to overcome any IM insufficiency issues and better represent each IM level. For example, regarding the seismic hazard, the ground motion records are selected to be site-specific and hazard-consistent (Lin et al. 2013; Kohrangi et al. 2017).

Figure 3: Single-stripe analysis results (adopted from Cornell and Jalayer 2002)

Figure 4: Multi-stripe analysis results of an asset subjected to multiple ground motions and indicative time-histories of scaled ground motion records that are used as the input for the analysis to get the IM-EDP pairs

3.4 Framework for performance assessment: fragility and vulnerability functions

The Performance-Based Earthquake Engineering (PBEE) framework as originally developed by Cornell and Krawinkler (2000) for the Pacific Earthquake Engineering Research Center, is employed for risk assessment in PLOTO. The PBEE methodology can be summarized as an implementation of the total probability theorem for calculating the mean annual frequency of violating (exceeding) a decision variable (DV), $\lambda(DV)$ as:

$$\lambda(DV) = \int_{DM} \int_{EDP} \int_{IM} G(DV | DM) |dG(DM | EDP)| |dG(EDP | IM)| |d\lambda(IM)| \tag{1}$$

where IM is the intensity measure, EDP is the engineering demand parameter (e.g., maximum roof/interstory drift ratio for a building), DM is the damage measure, DV is the decision variable, and $G(var_1 | var_2)$ is the probability that specified values of var_1 are exceeded given the level of var_2 . The final product of Eq.(1) is the mean annual frequency of exceeding the decision variable $\lambda(DV)$. Hence, risk can be estimated in terms of DVs that are also familiar with non-engineers, such as monetary loss, repair cost, casualties, and downtime. Figure 5 illustrates this risk assessment approach schematically. The five steps from exposure data to decision making as shown in Figure 5 are:

- **Exposure model:** it contains information on the assets at risk. Specifically, per asset of PLOTO information is provided about their location, taxonomy, value, vulnerability, etc.
- **Asset analysis:** MSA analysis is performed per asset considering all potential hazards affecting it to define its response and then to calculate the corresponding fragility curves.
- **Hazard analysis:** all the potential hazards to which assets are vulnerable are considered. The relationship between the severity (intense) of the excitation and the frequency with which each level of excitation is exceeded is defined.
- **Loss analysis:** the vulnerability function is defined for each asset given the environmental stressor intensity as measured by the pertinent IM. Vulnerability functions describe the distribution of a loss measure given the level of the IM. The loss is quantified in terms of repair cost, downtime, and functionality.
- **Decision making:** the results of risk assessment assist authorities and decision makers to establish prioritization protocols and to manage associated incidents, facilitating the rapid assessment of the state of the assets.

Figure 5: Natural catastrophe risk analysis framework (adopted from Porter 2019)

3.4.1. Fragility functions

Per asset, the continuous damage measure (DM) is discretized into a finite number of N damage states, DS_i ($i = 0 \dots N - 1$), separated by $N - 1$ associated limit-states, LS_i ($i = 1 \dots N - 1$). Each limit-state is associated with a predefined level of expected damages and typically is determined by a specific EDP threshold. The EDP threshold for exceeding LS_i indicates the appearance of DS_i until the EDP threshold for exceeding LS_{i+1} that indicates DS_{i+1} , etc. This way, fragility curves arise as continuous functions that provide the probability of exceeding a given LS_i , or equivalently of being in DS_i or worse, given the IM. A fragility function is defined as:

$$F_{LS_i}(IM) = F_{LS_i}(IM = x) = P[LS_i \text{ violated} | IM = x] = P[D > C_{LS_i} | IM = x] \quad (2)$$

where limit state LS_i violation is typically defined as the case where the seismic demand, D , exceeds the associated limit-state capacity, C_{LS_i} (typically defined by a single EDP threshold). Fragility curves are assumed to follow the lognormal distribution. In this way, if θ_i is the median value and β_i is the dispersion (logarithmic standard deviation) of LS_i , the probability of exceeding LS_i is calculated as:

$$F_{LS_i}(IM) = F_{LS_i}(IM = x) = \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(x / \theta_i)}{\beta_i}\right) \quad (3)$$

where $F_{LS_i}(IM)$ is the probability of exceeding LS_i given $IM = x$ and $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function. Then, the probability of being in each DS_i can be calculated as:

$$P(\text{in } DS_i | IM) = F_{LS_{i+1}}(IM) - F_{LS_i}(IM) \quad (4)$$

Damage states can be sequential, mutually exclusive or simultaneous. Sequential damage states are the norm, meaning that DS_{i+1} always succeeds DS_i , as damage/consequence in the structure increases. Usually, damage states escalate from the no-damage DS_0 to the total failure DS_N . Moreover, there are cases where a damage state can be defined as a mutually exclusive or simultaneous occurrence of higher-detail damage states (two or more). In the case of mutually exclusive DS s the occurrence of one DS precludes the occurrence of another. On the other hand, simultaneous DS may occur simultaneously, which is typical in a complex subsystem where different components may sustain damage simultaneously (e.g., the cabin and counterweight of an elevator). A typical example of fragility curves for three sequential limit states (four damage states) is presented in Figure 6.

Nonlinear dynamic analysis of numerical models is the basis for the most comprehensive analytical methods for assessing fragility. In PLOTO, MSA is used as the basis for analysing the response of the assets. Then, for given predefined EDP thresholds the corresponding fragility curves are calculated through MSA results per structure. Each fragility curve corresponds to a specific limit state of the structure. A typical example of the construction of a single fragility curve is presented in Figure 7. Specifically, a predefined EDP-threshold is set equal to 0.08 in the Peak Story Drift Ratio (8%, typical collapse level). Then, working per stripe (horizontal line in the IM-EDP space) the probability of exceeding the EDP-threshold (number of records that produce EDP demand higher than 0.08 / total number of records per single stripe) is calculated. The probability values per IM level structure the empirical cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the corresponding fragility function for the collapse limit state. Then, a statistical distribution (typically lognormal) is employed for fitting the empirical CDF in order to cover also the higher IM-levels (extremely rare events) where no analyses are performed. Thus, the full CDF of the collapse fragility curve is computed. Moreover, fragility curves can also be obtained directly via standardized tools that are available in the literature (e.g., HAZUS, FEMA 2003).

Figure 6: Example of fragility curves for three sequential limit states. The black arrowed lines indicate the probability of being in each damage state for a given value of the intensity measure

Figure 7: Example of MSA results (left) and discrete versus fitted collapse fragility function (right). (Adopted from Baker 2015)

3.4.2. Vulnerability functions

Vulnerability functions are probabilistic distributions that are employed for translating the physical damage of a structure into various parameters, such as monetary loss, repair duration, and downtime, given the level of the IM. The derivation of vulnerability functions involves two primary methods: direct empirical approaches and analytical methods. In the former, past event losses at specific locations with corresponding IM levels are considered, while the latter integrates fragility and consequence functions. Fragility functions describe the likelihood of reaching or exceeding a particular damage state based on the IM, and consequence functions represent probabilistic distributions of losses for given performance levels. The schematic depiction in Figure 8 outlines the analytical procedure for the estimation of vulnerability functions.

Figure 8: Framework for analytical estimation of vulnerability of a single asset (adopted from Porter 2019)

3.4.2.1. Earthquake, weather and non-flood vulnerability

Within the PLOTO platform, two approaches are used to define IWW and interconnected non-IWW assets' vulnerability curves:

Component-based vulnerability assessment approach

The approach of P-58 (FEMA, 2012) is followed for obtaining the vulnerability functions. According to this approach vulnerability functions are derived after correlating asset EDPs directly to loss. It requires detailed information regarding the fragility and loss functions on all vulnerable components per asset. Then, the mean vulnerability function per component category, the behaviour of which is controlled by EDP_i , is computed as:

$$E(L_i | EDP) = N_{i,h} \sum_{i=0}^{N_{ds}} P(ds_i | EDP) \cdot m_{i,ds} \quad (5)$$

where i is an index to the component category, L is the loss, N_{ds} is the number component damage states, $N_{i,h}$ is the number of the components of category i in group h , and $m_{i,ds}$ is the mean loss per unit of component category i in damage state ds .

System-only vulnerability assessment approach

In this approach system-level fragility curves are convolved with the cumulative consequence of an asset's damage state to assess the corresponding vulnerability functions. Thus, the mean vulnerability curve is calculated as:

$$E(L | IM) = \sum_{i=0}^{N_{DS}} E(L | DS_i) \cdot P(DS_i | IM) \quad (6)$$

where N_{DS} is the number of damage states, $P(DS_i | IM)$ is the probability of being in damage state i given the IM , $E(L | DS_i)$ is the expected loss (e.g., cost/downtime) given DS_i , and $E(L | IM)$ is the expected loss given the IM . Figure 9 presents an example of vulnerability curve estimation. The variance, $var(L | IM)$, of the vulnerability curve is computed as:

$$\text{var}(L | IM) = \sum_{i=0}^{N_{DS}} \left[\text{var}(L | DS_i) + E^2(L | DS_i) \right] \cdot P(DS_i | IM) - E^2(L | IM) \quad (7)$$

Vulnerability curves can be obtained by using Eq. (6) and Eq. (7) into a repetitive process for a range of IMs. Figure 10 illustrates some indicative results including the median (50%), 16%, and 84% quantiles of the vulnerability function.

Figure 9: Example of vulnerability assessment given fragility and deterministic consequence data (adopted from D’Ayala et al. 2015)

Figure 10: Example of the 16/50/84% fractiles of vulnerability curves in terms of cost computed using probabilistic cost distributions

The two approaches for estimating vulnerability function differ significantly. In the first one (FEMA P-58 approach), the asset is examined on a component basis regarding the damages and the consequences. To this end, taking for example an IWW asset sustaining DS_2 in its foundation is distinguished from one sustaining DS_2 in its roof. The first one can be seen as a severe damage, while the second one may be considered as a minor one that is easy to be repaired. On the other hand, in the second approach (system-only vulnerability), the entire system, namely the entire IWW or non-IWW asset, is characterized by a single DS leading to a coarse resolution regarding the determination of consequences.

3.4.2.2. Dike breaching and overtopping vulnerability

Figure 11: Operational diagram of the stressor modelling in Use Case C

This section introduces the computation of the stressors relevant for Use Case C (Wallonia), as detailed in deliverable D4.2, “Advanced and Reliable Models for Natural and Man-Made Hazards – Final Version.” Use Case C is particularly susceptible to flood hazard. Figure 11 summarizes the workflow

developed for estimating the stressors intensity, specifically the water levels in the considered waterway (Albert Canal) near potential dike breach locations, as well as the inundation extent and depths in the floodplains. The workflow contains 5 steps.

1. As sketched in the upper part of the flow chart in Figure 11, the workflow starts from meteorological forcings, either in the form of modelled precipitation quantities, or coming from observations. Precipitations data are necessary at several (virtual) stations across the hydrographic basin of interest (Meuse basin). When the evaluation of the stressors is based on climate modelling, the outcomes of a set of seven different bias-corrected climate models, combined with three distinct Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), are considered. Bias-corrected computed precipitation volumes are only available at a daily resolution. To force the AI-based hydrological model developed within PLOT0 (EXUS API), precipitation data at an hourly resolution are necessary. To this end, the outcomes of the climate models are disaggregated to an hourly resolution, at this stage by simply assuming a uniform distribution of rainfall intensity over a day.
2. The EXUS API is next used to forecast discharges at three locations corresponding to streamflow stations in Wallonia (Sauheid, Chaudfontaine, and Amay). Each discharge prediction by the EXUS API is based on the precipitation quantities over the past 25 hours. These input data are used to feed the module called “EXUS API and Use Case C Postprocessing” (coded in Python), which communicates with the EXUS API to retrieve a discharge prediction at the three considered locations.
3. These discharge predictions are used as upstream boundary conditions for a hydraulic model of the Meuse and the Albert Canal capable of reproducing the effects of dike breaching. Three main components may be distinguished in this modelling: (i) the flow processes in the main channels, (ii) the dike breach itself, which involves morphodynamic modelling of the breach evolution, and (iii) the flow processes in the floodplains. For each component of the model (main channels, dike breach location(s), and floodplains), models at two complementary levels of detail are developed, in line with the technical description provided in Deliverable D4.2. The reason for this is that the modelling aims to serve two distinct objectives:
 - modelling to support **planning**, which consists for instance in testing scenarios in a planning phase, with focus on the reliability of the model outcomes;
 - modelling in **operational** mode, such as for real-time forecasting, in which case the model computational efficiency is of primary importance.

In planning mode, the flow processes in the channels and in the floodplains are modelled using a detailed 2D gridded model, which is based on the full shallow-water equations. In contrast, for operational purpose, the spatially distributed flow models are replaced by simpler approaches, which may be either a lumped modelling (based mostly on mass balance and exchange equations) or a library of precomputed results from the detailed gridded model, from which results for other scenarios can be interpolated. A preliminary version of a lumped simplified modelling approach for the main channels is detailed in the last two paragraphs of this section. Hence, the detailed modelling layer feeds the operational one with data for parametrization of simpler models, or directly with precomputed model outcomes. In the developed approach, morphodynamic modelling of the breach evolution is handled by means of a physically-based, but spatially lumped

model, irrespective of the modelling mode (planning or operational). There are two main reasons for this:

- a. First, the problem is multi-scale: some aspects of the breaching mechanisms (such as lateral slope failures) occur over length scales way smaller than other lengths scales involved in the modelling, such as the main channel width or the extent of the floodplains. Capturing these relatively small-scale processes in a gridded model would require a grid strongly refined in the near-field of the breach, and this would strongly hamper computational efficiency.
- b. Second, dike breaching involves not only sediment transport but also complex geotechnical processes which are not properly captured by a standard shallow-water model coupled with Exner equation (i.e., the mass balance for sediments).

Therefore, for practical applications, these processes remain generally better reproduced through a lumped semi-empirical model. The dike breaching model used within PLOTTO is implemented in Python, and it dynamically interacts with the detailed flow model which is coded in Fortran. The coupling is set up with shared memory between the two codes.

4. The computed water levels in the main channel are used in combination with fragility functions characterizing the dikes resistance to determine the probability of dike breaching from the estimated water levels at potential breach points.
5. For each breaching scenario, the same hydraulic model as in Step 3 (i.e., either detailed or simplified) is used to determine the inundated areas and flow variables (inundation depths, flow velocity) in the flooded areas. These results enable generating danger maps and other products (e.g., visualization of the evolution of flow depths in the floodplains as a function of time), useful for the identification of assets at risk and for assessing impacts, such as monetary damages. These results will be used to guide the evaluation of possible mitigation measures, such as operating the weirs on the channels, so as to divert more water towards a different channel in case dike breaching is close to happen or is triggered in one of the channels.

Preliminary version of a lumped simplified modelling approach for main channels

The current version of the computationally-efficient hydraulic modelling approach (for use in operational mode) relies on simplifying assumptions, and is depicted on the flowchart of Figure 12. The discharges set as upstream boundary conditions (Sauheid, Chaudfontaine, and Amay) are currently summed up and injected at the confluence of the Meuse River and the Albert Canal, downstream of the centre of Liège. This assumption enables simplifying the topology of the actual network of waterways by reducing it to a single branch (Albert Canal, discretized in one dimension) where the dikes of interest are all located. A more elaborate approach, resolving the whole network of waterways (various branches of river Meuse, its derivation, the lower part of the tributaries Ourthe and Vesdre), is under development.

The main function of the Albert canal is to enable shipping. It is therefore equipped with navigation locks, and it can reasonably be modelled as a closed channel at its downstream end (Genk) by assuming the flood discharges of relevance for assessing flood hazard considerably exceed the discharges induced by water transfers due to lock operations. The downstream boundary of the river Meuse

model downstream of Liège is located at a mobile weir (Monsin). The prescribed boundary condition is a discharge-dependent value of water level. The Monsin weir regulates the level of the Meuse River to ensure a constant water level of 60.1m. When the discharge of the Meuse River discharge exceeds approximately 3700m³/s, the weir is no more able to control the water level, so that the water level upstream of the Monsin weir rises above 60.1m, affecting the water level distribution in the Albert canal. The water level distribution in the channel is computed by solving the 1D Shallow Water Equations, also known as dynamic Bernoulli equations. A potential dike breach location, identified by expert judgment, is used to initiate a breach and estimate flood propagation.

After estimating the effect of dike breaching, the analysis proceeds to flood vulnerability, which is presented in the next section (3.4.2.3).

Figure 12: 1st operational hydraulic modelling

3.4.2.3. Flood vulnerability

For the flood hazard determination of direct economic losses is conducted and is based on two types of flood damages to buildings: a) structure or building damages, i.e., damages to the building structural elements such as walls, doors, electrical panels, etc., and b) contents damages, i.e., damages to the items inside the building such as furniture, equipment that is not integral with the structure, computers, and other supplies (FEMA, 2012).

In general, the most common methodology to assess these direct economic losses is the application of the Depth-Damage Functions (DDFs) or Stage-Damage Functions, which quantify the flood damage that would occur at specific water depths. The development of such curves is mainly done empirically by collecting data on losses from previous flood occurrences, or synthetically based on experts' judgment. The provided values of damage may be absolute estimating damage in terms of currency or relative estimating the percentage of the maximum replacement cost of an asset. As for flood depth, in many cases, it is computed as the difference between the inundation depth and the elevation of the ground floor (plinth elevation) leading to damage factors relative (above or below) to the lowest floor which may result in negative flood-depth values.

A variety of DDF types is available in the literature depending on: a) flood source (riverine, coastal), b) flood duration, c) kind of asset (buildings, lands, vehicles), d) classification of assets usage ranging from general (residential, commercial, industrial, etc.) to more specific (residential single or multi-family dwelling, light or heavy industry, shops, churches, etc.), e) types of damage: structural/building, contents, inventory, f) the presence of basement, g) number of storeys, h) foundation type, i) location (site/country/continent), etc. Hence, for a comprehensive flood assessment, apart from a library of DDFs, additional data on assets attributes as well as census information are needed. Such approaches are implemented in "big models" like HAZUS.

For the PLOTO framework, the continental DDFs developed by Huizinga et al. (2017) are utilized. Those are not associated with specific type of floods (e.g., riverine or coastal) and therefore can be used for the damage assessment of a generic inundation event. They output damage factors (relative DDFs) for both structure and contents flood damages and are provided for six type of asset classes: residential/commercial/industrial buildings, transport, infrastructure-roads, and agricultural lands. Out of those, the first three are used and depicted in Figure 13.

For the calculations with DDFs the maximum structure and contents replacement values of each asset are evaluated by utilizing the country-wise valuation model proposed by Huizinga et al. (2017). The model relates a country's GDP per capita (x) to building construction cost (y) with the power function derived from regression analysis: $y = a \cdot x^b$, where a and b are damage class-specific parameters. The construction cost is adjusted by a modifier for the flood-resistant part of the structure, resulting in the maximum structure replacement unit value (€/m²). It must be noted that basements are valued differently; their replacement value is determined using the mean value from the average residential buildings class according to the HAZUS model. Contents replacement value is estimated as a percent of the structure replacement value. For this purpose, contents-to-structure-value ratios of 50%, 100%, and 150% for residential, commercial, and industrial assets, respectively, are applied as suggested by Huizinga et al. (2017). In addition, an inflation factor has been used to update all those values to 2024.

The maximum replacement unit value (€/m²) is multiplied by the flooded areas of an asset. The resulting value is multiplied by the damage factor derived from the DDF for a given flood depth so as to produce the estimate of the actual flood loss. Additionally, the replacement cost for all floors (both flooded and non-flooded) is calculated. The ratio of the flood loss of flooded asset areas to the replacement cost of all floors is then used to assign the asset to one of the "damage states": no damage (<1%), slight (1-10%), moderate (11-50%), or substantial (51-100%), in a similar manner which is implemented within the HAZUS model. The ratio of 50% is considered as the threshold for demolition (FEMA, 2004).

As for the computation part, the Flood Loss Assessment Module combines: 1) data on floodplain and flood depth for a given inundation scenario from a GeoTIFF file with 2) the exposure data from a shapefile, which must include attributes for each shape, such as asset area, height, number of stories, presence of a basement, damage class, etc. Each polygonal feature within the shapefile is matched to the corresponding flood depth obtained from the GeoTIFF floodplain. The module assigns an appropriate DDF to each feature, enabling the interpolation of damage factors. The results are compiled into a DataFrame, formatted as an attribute table, providing a structured overview of the flood loss estimates of the exposure. Such an approach enables flood loss data visualizations as illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 13: Depth-damage functions for residential, commercial and industrial buildings by Huizinga et al. (2017)

Figure 14: Exemplification of the results from the flood loss assessment methodology. The figure depicts the damage states of a set of building footprints within the floodplain for an inundation scenario

4. Applicable IWW and non-IWW assets

One of the main goals of PLOTTO is to assess the vulnerability and to improve the resilience of IWW and hinterland infrastructure under weather, flood, and seismic hazards. To do so accurately and robustly, a proper way to provide highly-detailed data for the assets is needed. In PLOTTO the assets per demonstration case are classified in two main categories; namely the *critical assets* (e.g., dikes) and the *less important yet non-negligible ones* (e.g., some warehouses, administration buildings). For the critical assets at risk, *asset-specific* estimates of fragility, vulnerability, and consequence functions are sought, where available. The seismic vulnerability of some assets, such as parking lots, container terminals, berths, and floating cranes, is not calculated, as it is considered negligible. Nevertheless, all these assets are included in the exposure model. All potential hazards of importance to each asset are considered and the entire potential range of stressors is mapped to their response, as well as the relevant damage at the detailed level of individual elements, where such information is available. Further to that, for the numerous lower importance assets, reduced-order *class-specific* models are employed in order to assess their performance in a robust way at a lower resolution with adequate accuracy at the ensemble level. In other words, regarding vulnerability assessment, critical assets are treated using asset-specific information, down to a component-basis when enough data is given, whereas a system-only approach is followed for the latter. All these assets jointly form the exposure model of PLOTTO. Furthermore, information gathered from traditional sensors positioned along the Inland WaterWays (IWW) and the surrounding infrastructure, combined with recorded climate-related data such as snow height, wind speed, and temperature variations is utilized to compare and calibrate simulation results.

The conceptual approach of FEMA P-58 is followed to assess the performance of all assets. The flowchart of this procedure is shown in Figure 15. Multiple potential scenarios that may occur on each asset are generated. For instance, regarding the assets treated via a component-based approach, for each IM scenario, the component's EDPs are calculated based on the MSA results (results stored in the *name.msa.mat/json* file). By convolving the fragility functions of each individual component with the associated consequence functions (stored in *name.mtdata.mat/json* file), multiple IM-DV (or intensity-to-consequences) scenarios are generated. Note that for each alternative IM scenario, if the asset has not collapsed (total failure), the consequences are calculated based on the cumulative damage and associated consequences sustained by each component. If the asset has collapsed, the consequences of replacing the asset are considered using global fragility and consequence functions. A similar methodology is followed for the performance assessment of the assets of lower importance that receive a system-only treatment, by employing system-only global fragilities (typically via tools like HAZUS) and consequence functions instead of component-based ones.

The data stored in MSA and metadata files per asset are processed and multiple potential damage/consequence scenarios are generated given all potential hazards that threaten the asset. By combining this information with the IM fields, which offer the spatial distribution of the selected IM, "all" potential scenarios that may happen on the portfolio of IWW and non-IWW assets are generated. This procedure enables a large-scale assessment of vulnerability of IWW, whereby loss, functionality, and downtime with a relatively low computational effort. Numerous "what-is" and "what-if" scenarios can be performed for the improvement of IWW resilience.

Figure 15: Flowchart for performance calculation (adopted from FEMA P-58)

Per use case of PLOTO various IWW and non-IWW assets consist of the portfolio of PLOTO exposure model. In the following sections the characteristic assets per Use Case are presented.

4.1 Use Case A

A brief description of the assets that refer to Use Case A (Danube Area, Romania) and constitute the exposure model of PLOTO for this Use Case is presented. For Use Case A, five different ports are considered, one in each of the following regions: Braila, Galati, Isaccea, Tulcea, and Sulina (Figure 16).

Figure 16: The five ports that make up the exposure model for Use Case A (Source Google Earth)

These assets mainly refer to cranes that are installed in the ports, warehouses that are used for storage and logistic operations, berths, and some office buildings. Figure 17 presents characteristic cranes that are installed at the Galati Port. These steel structures are mobile gantry cranes moving on rail tracks along quay wall.

Figure 17: Cranes installed at the port of Galati

Figure 18 presents a self-propelled floating crane installed at the Galati Port. Again, it is a steel structure that is a key part of the port facilities.

Figure 18: Self-propelled crane installed at the port of Galati

Warehouses are also assets related to the IWW port facilities. Figure 19 presents different types of warehouses that were constructed at the port of Galati. Figure 19a illustrates a warehouse that refers to a ground floor construction inside a port area (free zone) used to store raw materials. Figure 19b presents an open space warehouse used to store raw materials and big bags. These two warehouses are old structures. Figure 19c presents a newer warehouse that refers to a ground floor construction inside the Docuri Port area, which is used for logistic operation. It refers to a steel frame structure with steel panel closures.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 19: Characteristic warehouses at the port of Galati

At the Isaccea Port, which is located on the border with Ukraine, there are also “isobox” type office buildings covered by steel sheds, as shown in Figure 20a-c.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 20: "Isobox" type office buildings covered by steel sheds located at the Isaccea Port (Source Google maps)

In the Braila Port, the assets taken into consideration are two steel warehouses (Figure 21a-b), two mobile gantry cranes (Figure 21c-d), and one steel office building (Figure 21e).

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

Figure 21: Assets in Braila Port

In the Sulina and Tulcea Ports, only one reinforced concrete berth (Figure 22) and one reinforced concrete office building (Figure 23), respectively, were included in the exposure model.

Figure 22: Berth at the Port of Sulina (Source Google Earth)

Figure 23: Office building (Passenger Terminal) at the port of Tulcea (Source Google Earth)

Table 2 presents the main asset categories considered for the Use Case A of PLOTO along with their construction material, the natural hazard considered, and the IM(s) and EDP(s) that were defined for their vulnerability assessment.

Table 2: Use Case A asset types considered in PLOTO and corresponded hazard(s), IM(s), and EDP(s)

Assets	Types included	Material	Hazard	IM	EDP
Cranes	[-]	Steel	Earthquake, Wind Speed, Flood	$PGA / S_a(T)$, wind velocity	Deformations / Displacements / internal forces and moments, damage factor
Office buildings	Office buildings, passenger terminals, isoboxes with shelters	Reinforced concrete, steel, mixed concrete-steel	Earthquake, Wind Speed, Flood	$PGA / S_a(T)$, wind velocity	Deformations / Drifts Displacements / Internal forces and moments, damage factor
Industrial buildings	Warehouses	Reinforced concrete, steel, mixed concrete-steel	Earthquake, Wind Speed, Flood	$PGA / S_a(T)$, wind velocity	Deformations / Drifts Displacements / Internal forces and moments, damage factor

4.2 Use case B

Figure 24 presents the map view of the Port of Budapest. As illustrated, the port facilities include many assets that are part of the PLOTO’s exposure model.

Figure 24: Map view of the Port of Budapest. (Source Google maps)

Figure 25 presents the buildings that compose the port facilities followed by a coding system with a specific ID code assigned to each building. As shown, when compared to the map of Figure 24, some of the buildings shown in Figure 25 have not yet been constructed; still they have been planned as future structures (e.g., F1, F2, and F3 that refer to planned warehouses) or they are under construction (C5, D2). Moreover, building B5 has been demolished. The existing buildings shown in Figure 25 serve for various usages of the port. The majority of them refer to warehouses. There are very old warehouses (e.g., K2, K3, B7, and B8) as well as newer ones (e.g., C1, C2). Most of them refer to ground floor structures with total height ranging from 3.00m to 15.00m while two of the older ones (B7, B8) refer to tall buildings with multiple floors (Figure 26). Furthermore, the older warehouses are built with concrete or masonry. The newer ones refer to mixed concrete-steel structures. Figure 26 offers a general view of the port with some of the warehouses encoded in Figure 25 being denoted. There are also office buildings located within the Port (e.g., A10, A11, E3, E7, and Fer. 4). The majority of the existing office buildings refer to old or very old masonry buildings having 1 to 3 floors above the ground, while some of them also have underground floors. Moreover, there are buildings for special uses like the medical laboratory (B9) and the data center (D5).

Figure 25: Map view of the Port of Budapest with the ID codes assigned to the buildings (existing buildings, planned for construction buildings, demolished building B5)

Figure 26: General view of the Port of Budapest with some indicative buildings denoted. (Continued)

Figure 26: General view of the Port of Budapest with some indicative buildings denoted. (Continued)

Figure 26: General view of the Port of Budapest with some indicative buildings denoted

Except for the buildings, cranes are also structures related to the Port. Figure 27 presents the location on a map of existing cranes (No. 1–5). Cranes are made of steel. There are overhead cranes (e.g., No. 1, 3), container cranes (No. 4), and portal cranes (No. 5).

Figure 27: Location of cranes within the Port of Budapest (denoted with No. 1-5). (Source Google Earth)

Table 3 presents the main asset categories considered for the Use Case B of PLOTO along with their construction material, the natural hazard considered, and the IM(s) and EDP(s) that were defined for their vulnerability assessment.

Table 3: Use Case B asset types considered in PLOTO and corresponded hazard(s), IM(s), and EDP(s)

Assets	Types included	Material	Hazard	IM	EDP
Cranes	[-]	Steel	Earthquake, Wind Speed, Flood	$PGA / S_a(T)$, wind velocity	Deformations / Displacements / internal forces and moments, damage factor
Office buildings	Office buildings, cantina, medical lab, data centre	Reinforced concrete, masonry, steel, mixed concrete- steel	Earthquake, Wind Speed, Flood	$PGA / S_a(T)$, wind velocity	Deformations / Drifts / Displacements / Internal forces and moments, damage factor
Industrial buildings	Warehouses, ship service	Reinforced concrete, masonry, steel, mixed concrete- steel	Earthquake, Wind Speed, Flood	$PGA / S_a(T)$, wind velocity	Deformations / Drifts / Displacements / Internal forces and moments, damage factor
Development area	planned warehouses	mixed concrete- steel	Flood	[-]	damage factor

4.3 Use case C

Given the results of D4.2 for Wallonia, it is evident that the flood hazard dominates the risk for the buildings of interest. Therefore, the seismic risk is not considered to be of importance for Use Case C and will not be dealt with further. Based on the criticality of the flood hazard, the exposure of Case C consists of the dikes and buildings of the surrounding areas.

Dikes

For the Wallonia Use Case of PLOTO, dikes located in the Albert canal are the main type of assets that are considered in the exposure model. Figure 28 presents a map view of the Albert canal with the position of each different dike type being denoted. Dikes are usually made of earth fields, whereas also other materials may be used such as concrete. Different cases of dikes along the canal are then presented in Figure 29 to Figure 33. As shown in Figures from the topography graphs, for the East-dike of the Canal they have a height of around 6m, while their thickness varies from 4m to 20m.

Figure 28: Map view of the Albert canal form Lanaye to Coronmeuse. Red lines with the ID numbers number denote different types of dikes. (Source Google maps)

(a) East dike

(b) West dike

Figure 29: Dike at proximity of Lanaye bridge. The observable dike is highlighted in the topography graph. (Source Google maps)

(a) East dike

(b) West dike

Figure 30: Dike at proximity of Lixhe bridge. The observable dike is highlighted in the topography graph. (Source Google maps)

(a) East dike

(b) West dike

Figure 31: Dike at proximity of Haccourt bridge. The observable dike is highlighted in the topography graph. (Source Google maps)

(a) East dike

(c) West dike

Figure 32: Dike at proximity of Hermalle-sous-Argenteau bridge. The observable dike is highlighted in the topography graph. (Source Google maps)

(a) East dike

(b) West dike

Figure 33: Dike at proximity of Herstal bridge. The observable dike is highlighted in the topography graph. (Source Google maps)

Buildings

Dikes overtopping leads to floodplains of significant flood heights, which means that apart from the dikes themselves, the buildings situated in the vicinity of the Albert Canal are included in the PLOTO's exposure model, in order to examine the potential consequences on them owing to an inundation occurrence. Figure 34 presents instances of the typical buildings commonly found within the examined locations, which indicatively have been taken from some of them with the greatest interest, such as Loën, Haccourt, and Oupeye. As presented, in most of the cases, the buildings at the sites of interest are low-rise, meaning that they consist of one to three stories above the ground, whereas some also have basements (underground floors).

(a) Buildings at Loën

Figure 34: Typical building cases situated in the vicinity of the dikes of Wallonia Use Case. (Source Google maps). (Continued)

(b) Buildings at Haccourt

Figure 34: Typical building cases situated in the vicinity of the dikes of Wallonia Use Case. (Source Google maps). (Continued)

(c) Buildings at Oupeye

Figure 34: Typical building cases situated in the vicinity of the dikes of Wallonia Use Case. (Source Google maps)

The main asset categories considered for the Use Case C of PLOTO are shown in Table 4 along with the natural hazard(s) considered and the IM(s) and EDP(s) that were defined for their vulnerability assessment.

Table 4: Use Case C asset types considered in PLOTO and corresponded hazard(s), IM(s), and EDP(s)

Assets	Types included	Hazard	IM	EDP
Dikes	[-]	Flood	Water level	Flood water discharge
Residential buildings	Residential, nursing home	Flood	Water level	Damage factor
Commercial buildings	School, town hall, police, service station, place of worship, etc.	Flood	Water level	Damage factor
Industrial buildings	Industrial	Flood	Water level	Damage factor

4.4 Analysis of assets

After selecting the assets for the PLOTTO's exposure model, the analysis for the assets follows in order to assess their performance against the potential hazards per case. For each asset, the IM(s) and EDP(s) are defined, while the consequences are quantified in terms of e.g., monetary losses, downtime, and business disruption. The analysis is being made either via asset-specific models for the case of the critical assets or via class-specific models for the assets with lower importance. MSA or standardize tools for assessing structural fragility (e.g. HAZUS) are employed. For the assets of interest, each source of hazard (seismic, weather, and flooding) is analysed separately based on the location of the asset and the natural hazards associated with the site of interest.

5. Description of the structure of MHVM

The typical structure of Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Module is described in this section. The MHVM consists of two files per asset or class of assets:

- The first one is entitled “*asset_name.msa.mat/json*”, where “*asset_name*” is the name of the asset at hand. It includes the MSA results.
- The second one is entitled “*asset_name.mtdata.mat/json*”, which includes the metadata for each asset.

Data from both files are combined to assess the pre-event vulnerability per asset in order to generate multiple damage/consequences scenarios. These scenarios per asset are then combined with the IM fields to generate multiple alternative scenarios that may occur in the entire site (region) of interest per Use Case in the pre-event operation phase of PLOTO’s platform. This procedure is depicted indicatively in Figure 35. For cases where fragility is calculated via tools like HAZUS, the scenarios of damage/consequences are generated via the decomposition of the corresponding fragility functions. At this stage, risk assessment for the Use Case of interest is performed by considering all the “potential” scenarios that are calculated with their corresponding consequences in terms of damage and recovery being assessed by convolving the hazard results of all individual assets. This ensemble and detailed view of “all” events that can occur with the corresponding damage and loss that is predicted leads to a growing large “tree” of possible events, which can later be “pruned” in the trans-event operation phase. This pruning procedure aims to facilitate the goal of sensor-driven near-real-time assessment of PLOTO. Specifically, during the trans-event phase, which is the phase during which an event has just happened or happens in “real-time”, the limited information that is available from the sensors is employed to prune the full set of potential scenarios. Hence, a smaller and more manageable size of most probable outcomes is structured, which can lead the operators to better estimations of what is going to happen after that event in comparison with the full-fledged assessment of what could have happened (without sensor information).

Figure 35: Pre-event assessment of “all” potential scenarios of the Danube area, Romania by combining the MHVM with the IM fields

5.1 Metadata file

Per asset, the metadata file includes information regarding the fragility curves and the consequence functions for each damage state. For the assets that are treated via the system-vulnerability approach, the corresponding fragility curves are probability-valued functions of the IM of choice (e.g., the peak ground acceleration regarding the seismic hazard). In this case, the fragility functions provide information regarding the damage stage of the entire structure (asset) but they do not provide any specific information about its individual component. On the other hand, for the assets that are treated via a component-based approach, component-fragilities are offered in the metadata file that are constructed conditioned on the individual component’s EDP. In both cases, these fragilities are used in risk estimation.

The general format of the metadata file is the same for both assets treated via a system-only or component-based approach with only some details being different between them. The metadata file is named by the name or the ID of the asset (*asset_name*) followed by a predefined extension as “*asset_name.mtdata.mat/json*”. Except for the MATLAB “.mat” file, a “.json” format file is also created with the metadata per asset. This format is more suitable for assessing the risk of the entire network performed via Python software. Mat files are used to generate individual scenarios for the assets treated via a component-based approach. In this way, the metadata file of each individual asset can be stored either in “.mat” or “.json” file format and converted from one format to the other through available software.

5.1.1. Metadata file for the assets treated via a component-based approach

The typical structure of a metadata “.mat” and “.json” file is presented for the case of assets that are treated via a component-based approach. The files and the Figures that are presented herein do not consider specific cases from assets of PLOTO. They refer to indicative examples with dummy data that aim to describe the typical structure of the files necessary for the operation of the MHVM.

5.1.1.1. mtdata.mat file

Figure 36 presents a typical mtdata.mat file, generated through MATLAB. The metadata file consists of 5 fields. A description is provided for their structure and their contents for each one of these fields.

Figure 36: Example of a typical metadata file for assets treated via a component-based approach

- “.SerialNumberingFig”

A serial number per individual component is needed plus a figure with the serial numbers of the components studied across the asset. As an example, Figure 37 presents a bridge assumed to be an asset of interest. In this case, the bearings and the piers are the critical components of the asset. Hence a figure is stored in the field “.SerialNumberingFig” of the metadata file with the numbering of the components. It should be stressed out that the numbering should be aligned with the results of the multi-stripe analysis. For instance, regarding the piers, the MSA results for pier 1 (in terms of EDP) are found in the first entry of the MSA results file, the results for pier 2 in the second entry, etc.

Figure 37: Example of a typical figure of serial numbering and description of components for a bridge (stored in the .SerialNumberingFig field of the asset_name.mtdata.mat file)

- “.ComponentsData”

This field includes the data per individual component. In this field, generic categories of components are defined along with their associated engineering demand parameters (EDPs), fragility and consequence functions. Note that the engineering demand parameter should be the same as the corresponding EDLabel of the MSA results. An example of “.ComponentsData” field is shown in Figure 38, where the generic categories of the components “Bearing.001”, “Bearing.002”, and “Pier.001” are defined, along with the EDP that is selected per component (dummy data) and the associated Damage States (DS), fragility curves (*fragpar*), cost (*costpar*), traffic reduction (*trafredpar*), and downtime (*downtimepar*) functions. By moving a step forward in Figure 39, the structure of the DS and *fragpar* fields for a dummy component are presented. As shown, for this random component there are four (1–4) DSs defined, while in the *fragpar* field per DS (row), the corresponding fragility curve is assumed to follow the lognormal distribution (2nd column “logncdf”) with the parameters of the 3rd column of the field.

Fields	abc name	abc EDP	(1) DS	(1) fragpar	(1) costpar	(1) trafredpar	(1) downtimepar
1	'Bearing.001'	'maxbdr_srss'	1x4 cell	4x3 cell	4x2 cell	4x2 cell	4x2 cell
2	'Bearing.002'	'maxbdrx'	1x4 cell	4x3 cell	4x2 cell	4x2 cell	4x2 cell
5	'Pier.001'	'maxidr_srss'	1x4 cell	4x3 cell	4x2 cell	4x2 cell	4x2 cell

Figure 38: Example of definition of component’s data for a bridge (*asset_name.mtdata.mat*, *.ComponentsData* field)

ComponentsData(1).DS				
	1	2	3	4
1	1	2	3	4

(a)

ComponentsData(1).fragpar			
	1	2	3
1	1	'logncdf'	1x2 cell
2	1	'logncdf'	1x2 cell
3	1	'logncdf'	1x2 cell
4	1	'logncdf'	1x2 cell

(b)

Figure 39: Example of (a) damage states (DS) and (b) fragility curve definition for a component (*fragpar*) (*asset_name.mtdata.mat*, *.ComponentsData.DS* and *.ComponentsData.fragpar* field)

- “.Units”

The units of each consequence function are defined in the “.Units”. Figure 40 presents an example of the typical structure of this field. As it is shown except for the units, a short description of each consequence function is also provided.

Field	Value	Units.costpar	
(1) costpar	1x2 cell	1	2
(1) trafredpar	1x2 cell	euros	cost
(1) downtimepar	1x2 cell		

Figure 40: Example of consequence functions units definition (*asset_name.mtdata.mat*, *.Units* field)

- “.Components”

The “.Components” field contains information about the components of the specific asset that are considered for risk estimation. It is structured as a cell array in MATLAB whose $i = 1 \dots N$ (or $\{1, N\}$ contents in MATLAB terminology) entries correspond to the components with serial

number $i = 1 \dots N$ (Figure 37). Two entries are provided per component, which are (a) the name of the category of the component that has to be consistent with the naming of fragility and consequence functions (Figure 38) and (b) the number of such components. For instance, in the typical structure of the field illustrated in Figure 41, it is assumed that all bearings are of the same generic bearing type of ‘Bearing.001’ and the piers of type ‘Pier.001’.

```

% define the components of the asset
metad.Components{1}={'Bearing.001',1,'Pier.001',1};
metad.Components{2}={'Bearing.001',1,'Pier.001',1};
metad.Components{3}={'Bearing.001',1};
metad.Components{4}={'Bearing.001',1};
metad.Components{5}={'Bearing.001',1};
metad.Components{6}={'Bearing.001',1};

```

Figure 41: Example of component definition for a bridge (asset_name.mtdata.mat, .Components field)

- “.AssetsData”

In this field of the metadata “.mat” file some generic information about the asset is stored. This information can be generic collapse fragility and consequence functions of the asset that can be employed to define if the asset has collapsed. Also, in this field, data about the potential demolition of the asset and the consequences of replacing it can be stored.

5.1.1.2. mtdata.json file

A typical structure of a “.json” file with the metadata of an asset treated via a component-based approach is presented in Figure 42. The same information with the mat file is stored in “.json” files of an asset; only the format differs. Data shown in this Figure are dummy and do not refer to an IWW or non-IWW asset of PLOTTO’s exposure model. Still, Figure 42 aims to present the basic structure of a “.json” metadata file. As presented, the “units” and the “consequences_by_taxonomy” are initially set. For instance, “cost” and “euros” can be used to calculate economic consequences in monetary terms. The taxonomy is used to link each individual component with the fragility and consequence functions. Then, for the entire asset as well as for the components that are defined for the asset at hand, the “damage_types” are defined inside the “.json” file. Specifically, the name of each “component” is set with the “id” and the “description” of its “damage_states”. Then the “consequences_per_edp” is set where the “vuln_params” per component are defined.

Field	Value
IM	'PGA'
DS	1x4 cell
fragpar	4x3 cell
costpar	4x2 cell
trafredpar	4x2 cell
downtimepar	4x2 cell

Figure 44: Typical example of the structure of the .AssetsData field for asset treated via a system-only approach

Field	Value
costpar	1x2 cell
trafredpar	1x2 cell
downtimepar	1x2 cell

Figure 45: Typical example of the structure of the .Units field for asset treated via a system-only approach

5.1.2.2. mtdata.json file

The structure of a “.json” file with the metadata for an asset with system-only treatment is presented in Figure 46. As shown, the typical structure of the “.json” metadata file in this case is similar to that of the assets with the component-based treatment as above. The main difference is that instead of the data per individual component, the “global” data for the entire system are provided.

```

"mtdata": {
  "units": {
    "speed_limit": "km/h",
    "cost": "euros",
    "time": "days"
  },
  "Nrealizations": 100
},
"consequences_by_taxonomy": [
  {
    "asset_taxonomy": "Crane_PEQ1_PEQ1",
    "hazard_type": "seismic",
    "im_type": {
      "IM": "PGA",
      "IM_description": "peak ground acceleration",
      "IM_label": "PGA",
      "IM_units": "g"
    },
    "component_damage_state_description": [
      {
        "component": "global",
        "IM": "PGA",
        "damage_states": [
          {
            "id": "DS0",
            "description": "no damage"
          },
          {
            "id": "DS1",
            "description": "slight damage"
          },
          {
            "id": "DS2",
            "description": "moderate damage"
          },
          {
            "id": "DS3",
            "description": "extensive/complete"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  },
  "iml_consequences": [
    {
      "im_level": 0.00,
      "consequences": {
        "component": "global",
        "cost": [
          0.0,
          0.0,
          0.0,
          0.0
        ]
      }
    }
  ]
}

```

Figure 46: Example of the mtdata.json file for a crane asset treated via system-only approach

5.2 MSA file

The scenario MSA file consists of the MSA results for the IWW and non-IWW assets. Figure 47 presents the typical structure of the MSA file for a dummy asset.

Figure 47: (a) Typical example of a scenario MSA file and (b) variables stored in a scenario MSA file

5.2.1. Levels of the IM

Per hazard (stressor) considered for each asset of interest the following IMs are identified:

- **earthquake:** the array of IM levels includes the levels of the 5%-damped spectral acceleration, $S_a(T)$, or the peak ground acceleration, PGA . The values are stored in the variable “im_range” shown in Figure 47b.
- **wind:** two vectors are needed in this case. The first includes the wind speed (e.g., in m/s) and the second the direction of the wind (e.g., in degrees). Via the “meshgrid” function of MATLAB, the grid can be generated automatically.
- **temperature:** the temperature is typically provided in °C.
- **precipitation:** typically, the precipitation amount in mm over a given period is provided.
- **flooding:** typically, the water level in meters is provided.

5.2.2. EDP response levels

The EDP response per IM level is stored in the MSA response file as shown in Figure 47b. Specifically, the variables that are typically stored per component or per asset in the MSA response file are listed below:

- **EDPlabel:** strings containing the name of each of the *EDPs* recorded
- **EDPsublab:** strings containing a short description for each of the examined *EDP* variables
- **EDPval:** recorded *EDP* values
- **im_range:** range of *IM* values (i.e., stripe *IM* levels)
- **runs:** number of analysis runs per *IM* level
- **T_periods:** the first N vibration periods of the structure (where N is defined by the user in the structural analysis software)
- **thfilename:** the names of loading history file employed for asset analysis

For the specific case of the seismic response analysis, the following variables are also stored:

- **record_pga:** each record's (and component's) PGA
- **record_psa:** each record's (and each component's) pseudo- $S_a(T)$ values for each of the periods found in $T_periods$
- **record_sa:** each record's (and each component's) $S_a(T)$ values for each of the periods found in $T_periods$

6. Conclusions

This report is one of the two deliverables of WP4, related to Task 4.2 “Development of vulnerability modules”. In the previous report (D4.3 Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules for IWW and connected hinterland infrastructures 1st version, M18), the methodology behind the development of the multi-hazard vulnerability modules (MHVMs) was presented. The definition of basic quantities such as system’s fragility, vulnerability, and consequences were provided. Different approaches for assessing the risk/vulnerability/damage/loss were presented. Moreover, the characteristic assets that consist of the exposure model of PLOTTO were presented per Use Case site (Romania, Hungary, and Belgium). Finally, the typical structure of MHVMs as it is developed by using software libraries was described with indicative examples of the specific file’s structure being given. In this second version of the report (D4.4 Multi-Hazard Vulnerability Modules for IWW and connected hinterland infrastructures final version, M24), additional details are included regarding the flood vulnerability, the assets, the stressors that are related to them, as well as their treatment in the MHVM modules.

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